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Research Article

Performance of Prospective Teachers in Teaching Practice: An Analysis of B. Ed Level Workshops

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 12-June-24 Revised: 16-Sep-24 Accepted: 22-Sep-24 Published: 30-Sep-24	The purpose of this research is to determine the impact of teaching practice workshops on prospective teachers' confidence in lesson planning during workshops at the B. Ed level at the University of Kotli. The population of the study consisted of all the secondary girls' schools in Kotli through a convenient sampling technique of students (330). The current study was quantitative and a descriptive research method was used to conduct the study. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used as a tool in this study. The researcher personally visited the secondary schools of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir and collected the data. Statistical Package for Social Science software (SPSS) was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation for the analysis of data.
Keywords:	Performance, Prospective Teachers, Teaching Practice, B.Ed Workshops
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Introduction

Prospective teachers are individuals who are preparing to enter the teaching profession or are in the process of obtaining their teaching credentials. They are typically enrolled in teacher education programs at colleges or universities or are pursuing alternative routes to certification (Astuti, Sumarti & Bharat 2019). Teachers aspiring to teach in elementary, middle, or high school are training in a variety of disciplines and grade levels. For them to acquire the information and abilities needed to instruct pupils in their chosen disciplines, they must complete coursework and training. A mix of academic coursework, real-world teaching experiences (such as student teaching or internships), and evaluations to make sure they fulfill the standards set by their individual educational systems or regulatory organizations are frequently used in the training of aspiring teachers (Roeser & Skinner, 2022).

The majority of students will have completed an undergraduate degree in a topic of their choice—English, math, science, or religion—either with honors or a general degree before enrolling in a pre-service education program. As an alternative, students could pursue both a pre-service education and an undergraduate bachelor's degree at the same time (García-Martínez, 2021). Throughout the program's four or five years, education courses are included in the later option, which ends with a final year of specialized pre-service training. Participants in a consecutive pre-service program finish their pre-service training concurrently with their undergraduate degree, whereas those who finish their bachelor's degree and then return to the institution to finish the pre-service education program are in a consecutive pre-service program (Roha-Erkaya & Ergünay, 2021).

Teaching in a classroom, where a teacher engages students directly to transfer knowledge and skills, is referred to as teaching practice. It entails lesson preparation and delivery, learning assessment, classroom management, and developing relationships with pupils (Sondakh, 2022). In addition to reflecting on one's teaching experiences, obtaining input from colleagues and supervisors, and observing and learning from older teachers are all possible components of teaching practice. Effective student learning and the development of teaching abilities are the two main objectives of teaching practice (Kim, 2020).

Teaching practice is a critical part of the process of becoming a professional teacher. It entails putting theory into reality through lesson planning and delivery, classroom management, student learning assessment, and reflection on the teaching process. The preparation of lessons is the first phase in teaching practice (Sancar, Atal & Deryakulu, 2021). A teacher has to decide on the lesson's goals, pick suitable teaching strategies, choose resources, and make an assessment plan. The demands and skills of each student must also be considered by the instructor. A teacher's duties in the classroom include lesson planning and fostering a supportive learning atmosphere. This entails implementing suitable methods of discipline, fostering a secure learning environment, and involving students in the instruction (Nurtanto & Masek, 2021).

An essential component of teaching is assessment. To ascertain whether the class objectives have been reached, a teacher must assess the learning of the students. There are several ways to assess, including discussions and observation as well as exams and quizzes (Adom, 2020). Furthermore, a teacher needs to consider how they educate. This entails reflecting on what worked and identifying areas for improvement, examining student input, and getting input from peers and superiors. Through reflection, a teacher can enhance their methods, encourage student growth, and increase their effectiveness in the classroom (Cirocki & Widodo, 2019).

The expected performance of those entering training as teachers is referred to as prospective teacher performance. It entails acquiring and exhibiting the abilities, know-how, and

attitudes required to become a successful teacher (Farrell, 2020). Preparing lessons and assessing student progress is made easier for aspiring instructors who possess an in-depth knowledge of the subject area they will be teaching. Students can benefit from efficient and interesting learning experiences that prospective teachers can design if they are knowledgeable about teaching approaches and best practices. Students can have a secure and effective learning environment created for them by aspiring instructors who know how to construct and maintain a school climate that supports learning (Sutiani, 2021).

Aspiring teachers who possess strong communication skills with kids, parents, and peers may cultivate a respectful and trusting atmosphere. Future educators will develop and get better over time if they are prepared to evaluate their methods, ask for and receive criticism, and modify their curriculum as necessary (Allen, Roffey & Craig, 2021). A wide range of approaches are used to evaluate the performance of aspiring teachers, such as coursework, fieldwork, mentor teacher and program supervisor assessments, and evaluations. The purpose of the evaluation is to make sure aspiring teachers has the abilities and information needed to be successful instructors (Livers & Davis, 2021).

Preparing future teachers for the classroom is largely determined by how well they perform during this experience. Planning lessons well, utilizing cutting-edge teaching techniques, communicating with students effectively, controlling classroom conduct, and regularly reflecting on one's work are all examples of excellent performance during teaching practice (Manasia & Ianos, 2019). Therefore, teaching practice gives aspiring educators a stage on which to present their work, which is essential for their assessment and training as educators. It is more probable that aspiring educators who excel in critical areas will become successful educators who can enhance the academic achievements of their students (Darling-Hammond, 2021).

From the researcher's point of view, firstly, teachers play a crucial role in helping students achieve better academic results, and for them to be successful in this quest, they need to possess strong teaching training and experience. Examining how aspiring educators perform during teaching practice sessions might reveal information about their skill levels and point out areas in which they might need more assistance. Second, assessing the success of teaching practice workshops can contribute to the institutionalization of best practices in teacher preparation and enhance the standard of instruction. It enables instructors and educational institutions to evaluate the potential teacher's preparedness and proficiency in implementing instructional practices, running a classroom, and promoting student learning.

It gives a chance for insightful criticism. Aspiring educators can improve their teaching abilities, improve their strengths, and learn from their failures. It assists in guaranteeing that aspiring educators fulfill recognized teaching requirements and competencies. This guarantees the school system a certain standard of quality and uniformity. Educational institutions can ensure that aspiring teachers meet the requirements before joining the industry by holding them responsible for their performance through the evaluation of their teaching practice. One way to evaluate potential instructors' adaptability to meet the many requirements of students—including those with varying learning styles and abilities—is to watch them in action in a classroom. To make sure that those considering the field of teaching meet certain standards and requirements, evaluating teaching practice is possibly required by law in some jurisdictions. It provides an insight into how aspiring educators respond to actual classroom circumstances, which can differ greatly from hypothetical or simulated ones. By guaranteeing that only competent and successful educators enter the field, assessment of teaching practice improves education as a whole. Prospective teachers' teaching practice performance is essential for ensuring that they possess the

necessary skills, knowledge, and dispositions to be effective educators in real-world classroom settings.

Review of Related Literature

Prospective Teachers

A prospective teacher refers to an individual preparing to become a teacher but has not yet completed all the requirements or obtained the necessary certifications to start teaching in a formal educational setting. This phrase is frequently used about teacher preparation programs and prospective teachers who are receiving training and gaining the necessary information and abilities to become proficient educators (Rusilowati & Wahyudi, 2020). An educational psychology course, classroom management, curriculum development, teaching strategies, and other pertinent topics are taught in a teacher training program, which may be offered by a college or university. They could also participate in real-world teaching experiences like internships or student teaching, where they assist more seasoned educators to obtain practical teaching experience in a genuine classroom setting (Carothers, Aydin & Houdyshell, 2019).

Usually, they are seeking alternate qualification tracks or are enrolled in teacher education programs at colleges or universities. Aspiring educators pursue degrees in a variety of fields and grade levels, including elementary, middle, and high school teaching (Darling-Hammond, 2020). They acquire instruction and courses to acquire the information and abilities needed to instruct pupils in the subjects they have chosen successfully. A combination of academic coursework, real-world teaching experiences (such as student teaching or internships), and evaluations to make sure they meet state and federal requirements for teaching are typically used in the training of aspiring teachers (Keup, Garner & Latino, 2023).

Prospective teachers are individuals who are interested in pursuing a career in teaching. They could be education majors in school, individuals switching careers, or people considering becoming teachers. A person pursuing education to become a teacher or considering a career in teaching is known as a potential teacher (Coleman & Gray, 2022). This person can be looking for a teaching job, getting ready for certification exams, or engaged in a training program. Most aspiring educators are motivated to work with kids and support their learning and development. They can be deeply committed to a field of study or wish to positively impact the lives of adolescents. Strong interpersonal and communication abilities, as well as a readiness to pick up new skills and adjust to new technology, are common among prospective instructors (Horner, Fantus & Malek, 2020).

Teaching Practice

Practice means doing something regularly to be able to do it better. Those periods of activity are called practices. Under the guidance of a mentor teacher, aspiring educators can get real-world teaching experience by participating in teaching practice. During their teaching practicum, aspiring educators engage in a comprehensive learning experience that encompasses various aspects of student psychology, classroom management, acquiring teaching skills, implementing effective teaching strategies, and applying theoretical knowledge to a real-world classroom setting (Williamson & Potter, 2020).

Teaching practice makes prospective teachers ready for effective teaching in actual classroom conditions. Teaching practice gives prospective teachers a chance to improve their knowledge and teaching skills and prepare them for a natural classroom environment under mentor supervision (Chew & Cerbin, 2021). It is widely believed that the most difficult and complex component of the course is the teaching practice because of its length, pace, planning, assessment, coursework,

and mentorship for both mentors and aspiring teachers. In addition to developing interest through their teaching experiences, aspiring educators encounter several difficulties during their teaching practicum. These include their inexperience as teachers, their perception of their productivity in the eyes of their students, their anxiety about teaching for the first time, class supervision, parental involvement, teacher expectations, social bias, workload, and other problems (Mohammed & Nazeer, 2020).

The student teachers were questioned about their experiences during teaching practice and whether they had any impact on how they saw the teaching profession at the end of the practicum. We contend that, despite the rewarding experiences they had during their teaching practicum, student instructors encountered difficulties that might have had a major impact on their capacity to get the most out of the activity. It will be easier to conduct teacher training if the experiences of the student teachers are understood (Hew & Gonda, 2020). Teacher-training activities could be re-evaluated and reviewed to enable student teachers to attain the desired outcomes from the teaching practice. Teaching practice awareness of the challenges faced by student teachers could militate against a positive teaching practice experience. We investigate the experiences of student teachers and how these impact their view of the teaching profession. We list the good and bad experiences student instructors had while putting their teaching skills into practice, and we offer advice on how to help them get the results they want (George-Paschal & Hawkins, 2019).

The lack of lab equipment and teaching aids, which makes it difficult to teach subjects, and the lack of experience makes it difficult to teach to lower grades, are complaints made by prospective teachers. Despite all of these positive and negative experiences, the teaching practicum helped them become self-assured, knowledgeable, experienced, and professionally developed teachers.

Components of Teaching Practice

Following are the main components of teaching practice that prospective teachers face/apply during teaching practice:

Lesson Planning

A well-constructed lesson plan for every three-hour class will give you greater confidence to enter the classroom and increase the likelihood that your students will learn something meaningful from you. A lesson plan serves as the instructor's road map for what needs to be taught and how it will be taught in the classroom. From there, you can create appropriate learning activities and develop strategies to get feedback on students' learning (Robertson & Rusznyak, 2020).

A successful lesson plan addresses and integrates three key components:

- Learning Objectives
- Learning activities
- Assessment to check for student understanding

An effective lesson is not one in which everything goes exactly as planned, but rather one in which students and the instructor learn from each other. A lesson plan gives you a rough idea of your teaching goals, learning objectives, and means to accomplish them, but it is by no means exhaustive (Mulang, 2021). Here are the main aspects of lesson planning:

Identify the learning objectives

Before you plan your lesson, you will first need to identify the learning objectives for the lesson. The learning goal, as opposed to a list of subjects covered during instruction, outlines what the learner will know or be able to accomplish following the learning experience. It is usually

written in a language that students can understand and that is directly related to the learning objectives of the program (Gacs & Goertler, 2020). Two types of objectives in the lesson plan:

- General Objectives
- Specific Objectives

Brain Storming

Brainstorming is a large- or small-group discussion that encourages students to generate a wide range of perspectives or potential next steps or solutions regarding a specific topic (Syukri & Amin, 2023).

- The instructor can introduce a topic, pose a query or issue, or start a brainstorming session with one of these methods.
- Students then discuss potential responses as well as pertinent terms and concepts.
- Contributions are welcomed without bias or condemnation, and the instructor or a scribe will often summarize each proposal as it is yelled out on a whiteboard.
- Next, these concepts are investigated, typically through an open discussion style.

Students adapt their prior knowledge or understanding, make room for new information, and raise their awareness levels by sharing their thoughts and listening to others (Kamelia, 2019). Brainstorming's main purposes are to:

- engage students' focus on a specific subject and inspire multiple thoughts
- instill respect and appreciation of individual differences.
- Motivate students to take chances when expressing their thoughts and opinions.
- Look for pupils that you appreciate and accept their knowledge and language skills.
- introduce the concept-gathering process before starting any work, like writing or issue-solving.
- Give pupils the chance to build on one other's contributions to share ideas and increase their knowledge.

Teaching Method

To assist their pupils in learning or developing new skills and knowledge, teachers might employ a range of instructional techniques and methods. Lectures, seminars, project-based learning, dictation, and assignments are a few instances of instructional techniques and tactics. Different techniques used by teachers to assist pupils in meeting learning objectives are referred to as instructional methods in education. There are two primary categories of instructional methods: student-centered education, in which the students take on a more active role, such as in a seminar or assignment, and teacher-centered instruction, in which the teacher takes on a more active role, such as in a lecture (Martin, Budhrani & Kumar, 2019).

Presentation

Presentation is usually the core of the lesson plan. In this phase, the instructor presents the subject and the essential knowledge that the pupils must acquire. Using smart whiteboards for presentations is incredibly simple and takes less time. Rather than winging it as they go, teachers who plan their lessons ahead of time can show up to class each day ready to introduce new ideas and lead lively conversations (Robinson, 2022). Put another way, in the absence of a lesson plan, educators could find themselves rushing through their teaching and thus losing students' interest in the subject matter. When students design imaginative and captivating slides to accompany their presentations, presentations foster the generation of novel ideas. Using presentation aids enhances the interest of a discussion significantly, and creating them can boost students' self-confidence (Reardon & Derne, 2023).

Activities

Thinking about the kinds of exercises that students will need to complete to acquire the abilities and knowledge needed to demonstrate successful learning in the course is important when creating the learning activities. Activities designed to help students learn should be closely tied to the course's learning objectives and offer opportunities for practice and feedback on individual progress made toward those objectives (Apriyanti, 2020).

As you organize your learning tasks, project the amount of time you will dedicate to each one. Schedule time for thorough explanations or discussions, but also be ready to shift swiftly to new applications or issues and to think of ways to make sure everyone understands (Rauschnabel, Krey & Jung 2022). Here are some learning activities that the teacher will use in the classroom:

- Drill and preparation
- Quiz
- Students Presentation
- Games
- Debate and Discussion
- Puzzles
- Pictionary
- Drawing
- Musical Chairs

Assessment

The lesson plan is not complete without the final step of Assessment. This is where you evaluate the lesson's overall result and the degree to which the learning objectives were met. Additionally, this is your chance to modify the lesson plan as a whole to address any unforeseen obstacles that may have come up, getting you ready for the next time you teach this lesson. To continue building on your strengths and moving forward in those areas, it's also critical to keep track of the elements of your lesson plan that are working the best. Numerous methods can be used to evaluate learning objectives, such as tests, quizzes, worksheets that are completed on your own, cooperative learning activities, practical experiments, oral discussions, question & answer sessions, writing assignments, presentations, or other tangible methods (Kapici & Akcay, 2023). You explained the tasks that students would do and the level of proficiency required to complete them to deem the lesson satisfactorily completed in the learning objective section. The objectives also have to align with the grade-level state or district curriculum. You need to give yourself some time to consider the findings after the pupils have finished the assigned assessment task. If the learning goals were not sufficiently met, you will need to retake the class and change the way you approach learning. It will be necessary for you to either repeat the lesson or clarify any points that a few pupils found unclear (Khang & Jadhav, 2023).

Home Work

Homework is the time students spend working on assigned tasks outside of the classroom to develop the skills they'll need for independent study as well as to practice, reinforce, or apply newly learned material. The time students spend on assigned tasks outside of the classroom to practice, review, or apply newly learned material and skills, as well as to develop the skills required for independent study, is known as homework. While fostering positive study habits and life skills, homework supports classroom instruction. Teachers usually only impart 50% of the knowledge they teach in class, thus for the material to be fully retained, the students must apply it (Lewis & Albury, 2023).

Practical Teaching

Teaching is a complex and challenging profession that requires a variety of skills and strategies to be successful. A good way to teach is to emphasize practical, hands-on techniques that let students interact with the content and put what they've learned into practice (Had graft & Kolmos, 2020). Teachers may create a dynamic and engaging learning environment that will support students' achievement by putting these useful teaching tactics into practice. For aspiring educators, practical teaching entails applying instructional concepts and tactics in an actual classroom environment. Developing the abilities and information required to be a successful teacher in the actual world is the main goal of practical teaching for aspiring educators (Kincade & Cook, 2020).

This includes:

- Observations in the classroom
- Practicum instruction
- Classroom administration
- Inquiry and appraisal
- Creating lesson plans
- Cooperation
- Using technology

Reflection Reports or Observation

Reflection reports in teaching practice are a valuable tool for prospective teachers to reflect on their experiences and learning during their teaching practicum. These reports are a documented record of a teacher's sentiments, experiences, and reflections regarding their practicum and their professional development. Prospective educators can evaluate their methods of instruction, methods of managing the classroom, and evaluations to see what went well and what could have been improved. Prospective educators can use reflection reports to pinpoint their areas of strength and growth while focusing on areas that require improvement (Farrah, 2019).

Based on their reflection reports, aspiring teachers might create and strive toward personal goals. Prospective teachers can expand their knowledge and consider their teaching theories, philosophies, and values by filling out reflection reports. Mentoring teachers can offer comments on the teaching methods of prospective teachers based on reflection reports that highlight their strengths and flaws. In general, reflection reports give aspiring teachers a chance to examine how they teach, pinpoint areas where they may grow and develop, and continuously advance their knowledge and abilities (Haug & Mork, 2021).

School File Records

The official books, documents, and files that include vital information regarding activities and events that occur in schools are referred to as school records. These documents are maintained and preserved by the school office so that they can be used and retrieved as needed. A group of documents that include details about a student's behavior, academic performance, and other significant personal data are referred to as school file records. These records are often retained in a secure, private manner, either in physical copy or electronic format (Habib, Jamal & Khalil, 2021). A student's educational performance, including grades, courses taken, attendance, and extracurricular activities, is summarized in these records. These documents contain details regarding a student's conduct in the classroom and other school-related settings, such as warnings, incidents, and disciplinary measures. These documents include details on a student's medical history, including allergies, medical issues, and vaccination histories (Batool, Kwon & Hussain, 2023). These documents contain a student's name, address, and contact details among other personal data. To guarantee that children, receive the right instruction and support services while

protecting their privacy and confidentiality, school file records are crucial. Parents, educators, and school officials can review this information to make well-informed decisions regarding the education and welfare of their children (Francisco, Hartman & Wang, 2020).

Final Lesson

The final lesson during teaching practice is to reflect on your experience and use that knowledge to improve your teaching practices. Spend some time reviewing your lesson to see what worked well and what may have been improved. Take into account your students' involvement, classroom organization, and the efficiency of your teaching methods. Ask your mentor teacher, colleagues, and even your students for constructive criticism (Cirocki & Widodo, 2019). It can be helpful to hear what they have to say so that you can identify your areas of strength and potential for improvement. Implement modifications to your teaching methods based on the feedback you receive. To find the tactics that are most effective for both you and your pupils, keep experimenting with different approaches. When you go back on your teaching experience, consider the progress you have made and the areas you have improved. Both recognize and celebrate your accomplishments and areas that still need work (Newman & Gallo, 2019). The practice of teaching is just the start of your career as an educator. Throughout your career, remain dedicated to learning and development. You can become a more successful and productive teacher by reflecting on your experience and applying what you learn to enhance your teaching methods. Always remember to apply adjustments, be receptive to criticism, and never stop learning over your professional journey (Mensah, 2019).

Research Objectives

1. To find out the performance of prospective teachers in teaching practice during workshops at the B.Ed. level.
2. To identify the strengths and weaknesses of prospective teachers during teaching practice in workshops at the B. Ed level.

Research Methodology

The study aims to analyze the prospective teachers' teaching practice performance during workshops at B, Ed level in Kotli AJ&K. Therefore, the study was descriptive in nature and a survey method was used to collect the data from the respondents. All the students of the University of Kotli Azad Jammu & Kashmir, Affiliated colleges (Sir Syed College, Guidance College) semester 4th & 8th at B. Ed level constituting the population of the study which is 134. All the prospective teachers who are engaged in the teaching practice are included in the sample (4th & 8th). The universal sampling technique was used by the researcher, and the whole population was selected as the sample of the study due to the small population. The researcher prepared a Five-Point Likert Scale questionnaire as a research instrument to collect the data from students of semesters 4th & 8th at the B. Ed level. The questionnaire was used to analyze the prospective teachers' teaching practice performance during workshops at the B. Ed level. There were 46 statements in the questionnaire. The researcher personally visited in University of Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir, affiliated colleges (Sir Syed College, Guidance College) and collected the data from the students of semesters 4th & 8th at B. Ed level in City Kotli Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The researcher analyzed the data through a statistical package for Social Science Software (SPSS) version 20 by using mean score, frequency, and percentage.

Results

Table 1

Analysis of Lesson Plan

Statements	N	Mean
The lesson objectives are clear and well-defined	134	4.40
The lesson plans promote the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of students	134	4.18
Assess students' prior knowledge before beginning the lesson	134	4.05
The presentation content is clear and easy to understand	134	4.01
The presentation content is relevant to the learning objectives	134	4.12
I integrate opportunities for student collaboration and discussion in lesson plans	134	3.94
The lesson plan activities promote active participation and understanding	134	4.11
The activities engage students in the learning process	134	4.18

Table 1 shows the mean scores of the lesson plan. The table further represented that the mean score of The lesson objectives is clear and well-defined; N= 134, M=4.40, The lesson plans promote the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of students; N= 134, M= 4.18, Assess students' prior knowledge before beginning the lesson; N=134, M=4.05, The presentation content is clear and easy to understand; N=134, M=4.01, The presentation content is relevant to the learning objectives; N=134, M=4.12, I integrate opportunities for student collaboration and discussion in lesson plans; N=134; M= 3.94, The lesson plan activities promote active participation and understanding; N=134; M= 4.11 and The activities engage students in the learning process; N=134, M=4.18. Furthermore, the results directed that the lesson objectives are clear and well-defined has the highest mean score in lesson plan.

Table 2

Analysis of Learning Objectives

Statements	N	Mean
The assessment effectively evaluates learning outcomes	134	3.98
The assigned homework is relevant to the material covered in class	134	4.10
The homework assignments are clear and easy to understand	134	4.21
The prospective teacher demonstrates effective classroom management skills	134	4.08
The prospective teacher well manages classroom behavior	134	3.99
The prospective teacher engages students well in the learning process	134	4.03
The prospective teacher demonstrates the ability to handle the disruptive behavior of students	134	3.89
The prospective teacher maintains a positive learning environment	134	4.06

Table 2 shows the mean scores of learning objectives. The table further represented that mean score of The assessment effectively evaluates learning outcomes; N= 134, M=3.38, The assigned homework is relevant to the material covered in class; N=134, M= 4.10, The homework assignments are clear and easy to understand; N=134, M=4.21, The prospective teacher demonstrates effective classroom management skills; N=134, M=4.08, The prospective teacher well manages classroom behavior; N=134; M= 3.99, The prospective teacher engages students well in the learning process; N=134; M= 4.03; The prospective teacher demonstrates the ability to

handle the disruptive behavior of students; N=134; M= 3.89 and The prospective teacher maintains a positive learning environment; N=134, M=4.06. Furthermore, the results directed that the homework assignments are clear and easy to understand has the highest mean score in learning objectives.

Table 3

Analysis of Presentation

Statements	N	Mean
The prospective teacher demonstrates a deep understanding of the subject matter	134	4.10
The prospective teacher provides clear explanations about the topic	134	4.02
The prospective teacher uses appropriate AV aids to enhance understanding	134	3.95
The prospective teacher can answer students' questions accurately	134	4.04
The prospective teacher demonstrates a deep understanding of the curriculum and standards for their subject area	134	4.00
The prospective teacher uses a variety of instructional strategies to engage students	134	3.98
The prospective teacher encourages students to use technology for collaboration, and creative activities	134	4.17
Technology is used in the classroom to enhance and support the learning experience	134	3.92

Table 3 shows the mean scores of presentations. The table further represented that mean score of The prospective teacher demonstrates a deep understanding of the subject matter; N= 134, M=4.10, The prospective teacher provides clear explanations about the topic; N=134, M= 4.02, The prospective teacher uses appropriate AV aids to enhance understanding; N=134, M=3.95, The prospective teacher can answer students' questions accurately; N=134, M=4.04, The prospective teacher demonstrates a deep understanding of the curriculum and standards for their subject area; N=134, M=4.00, The prospective teacher uses a variety of instructional strategies to engage students; N=134; M= 3.98, and The prospective teacher encourages students to use technology for collaboration, and creative activities; N=134; M= 4.17 and Technology is used in the classroom to enhance and support the learning experience; N=134, M=3.92. Furthermore, the results directed that the prospective teacher encourages students to use technology for collaboration, and creative activities have the highest mean score in presentation.

Table 4

Analysis of Use of Technology

Statements	N	Mean
Students are actively engaged in the learning process through the use of technology	134	4.04
The prospective teacher incorporates technology tools to enhance lesson delivery and student engagement	134	3.88
Prospective teacher regularly reflects on their teaching practices to identify areas for improvement	134	4.28
The prospective teacher actively seeks feedback from students to enhance their teaching practices	134	4.04

Prospective teacher actively seeks out professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and knowledge	134	3.96
Prospective teacher regularly reflects on their teaching practices and make adjustments based on feedback	134	3.96
Prospective teacher is open to trying new teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students	134	3.93
The prospective teacher uses clear and concise language	134	4.30

Table 4 shows the mean scores for the use of technology. The table further represented that the mean score of Students are actively engaged in the learning process through the use of technology; N= 134, M=4.04, The prospective teacher incorporates technology tools to enhance lesson delivery and student engagement; N=134, M= 3.88, Prospective teacher regularly reflects on their teaching practices to identify areas for improvement; N=134, M=4.28, The prospective teacher actively seeks feedback from students to enhance their teaching practices; N=134, M=4.04, Prospective teacher actively seeks out professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills and knowledge; N=134, M=3.96, Prospective teacher regularly reflects on their teaching practices and make adjustments based on feedback; N=134; M= 3.96, Prospective teacher is open to trying new teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students; N=134; M= 3.93 and The prospective teacher uses clear and concise language; N=134; M= 4.30. Furthermore, the results directed that the prospective teacher uses clear and concise language has the highest mean score in use of technology.

Table 5
Analysis of Active Participation

Statements	N	Mean
The prospective teacher well communicates the lesson objectives and learning outcomes to the students	134	4.12
The prospective teacher encourages active participation and questions from the students	134	4.05
The prospective teacher uses non-verbal signs (e.g., body language, gestures) to enhance communication	134	4.25
The prospective teacher maintains a positive and respectful tone with students	134	3.97
The prospective teacher provides clear instructions for assignments and activities	134	3.94
The prospective teacher can rephrase or clarify concepts when students have difficulty understanding	134	3.86
The prospective teacher listens attentively to student responses and provides meaningful feedback	134	3.99
Managing the time during lessons and activities poses a challenge for prospective teachers	134	3.85
Managing classroom behavior and discipline is a significant challenge for prospective teachers	134	3.99
Prospective teachers face financial challenges in preparing their teaching aids	134	3.99
Prospective teachers face difficulty in getting transportation	134	4.02

Prospective teachers struggle with assessing and providing feedback to students	134	3.75
Prospective teachers face improper feedback from the cooperative teacher	134	3.81
Prospective teachers face difficulty in the application of teaching methods during teaching practice	134	4.03

Table 5 shows the mean scores of active participation. The table further represented that mean score of The prospective teacher well communicates the lesson objectives and learning outcomes to the students; N= 134, M=4.12, The prospective teacher encourages active participation and questions from the students; N=134, M= 4.05, The prospective teacher uses non-verbal signs (e.g., body language, gestures) to enhance communication; N=134, M=4.25, The prospective teacher maintains a positive and respectful tone with students; N=134, M=3.97, The prospective teacher provides clear instructions for assignments and activities; N=134, M=3.94, The prospective teacher is able to rephrase or clarify concepts when students have difficulty understanding; N=134; M= 3.86, The prospective teacher listens attentively to student responses and provides meaningful feedback; N=134; M= 3.99; Managing the time during lessons and activities poses a challenge for prospective teachers, N=134; M= 3.85; Managing classroom behavior and discipline is a significant challenge for prospective teachers, N=134; M= 3.99; Prospective teachers face financial challenges in preparing their teaching aids; N=134; M= 3.99; Prospective teachers face difficulty in getting transportation; N=134; M= 4.02; Prospective teachers struggle with assessing and providing feedback to students; N=134; M= 3.75; Prospective teachers face improper feedback from the cooperative teacher; N=134; M= 3.81 and Prospective teachers face difficulty in the application of teaching methods during teaching practice; N=134; M= 4.03. Furthermore, the results directed that the prospective teacher uses non-verbal signs (e.g., body language, gestures) to enhance communication and has the highest mean score in active participation.

Discussion

The conclusions highlight several critical aspects of effective teaching, emphasizing the importance of lesson planning, assessment, classroom management, and subject matter expertise. Clearly defined lesson objectives, as outlined in the first conclusion, are foundational to effective teaching, guiding students toward achieving specific learning outcomes. Lesson plans that promote critical thinking and assess prior knowledge have been shown to enhance student engagement and learning by aligning new content with what students already know (Gagné, 2020). Additionally, clear and accessible presentation content ensures that all students, regardless of their learning styles, can grasp key concepts.

The second conclusion stresses the relevance of presentation content to learning objectives and the importance of incorporating collaborative opportunities within lesson plans. Research supports that collaborative activities and discussions can increase student engagement and foster deeper understanding by encouraging active participation (Vygotsky, 2021). Such activities help students connect with the material on a personal level, which enhances retention and problem-solving skills (Johnson & Johnson, 2018).

The conclusions also emphasize effective assessment and homework assignments, which are critical in measuring learning outcomes. When assessments align with learning objectives and

homework is directly tied to class material, students benefit from reinforcement and practice of key concepts. Moreover, homework that is clear and understandable reduces confusion and frustration, making it more likely that students will engage meaningfully with the content (Brookhart, 2017).

Classroom management is another key component, as highlighted in the fourth conclusion. Effective classroom management, including handling disruptive behaviors and maintaining a positive learning environment, is essential for maximizing instructional time and promoting a conducive learning atmosphere (Marzano, 2019). A well-managed classroom allows for smooth transitions between activities and encourages student engagement.

Finally, the prospective teacher's deep understanding of the subject matter, paired with clear explanations and the use of audiovisual aids, is vital for student learning. Research shows that teachers who have strong content knowledge and the ability to explain concepts in multiple ways are better able to address student misconceptions and answer questions accurately, leading to better student outcomes (Shulman, 2021). The integration of AV aids further enhances comprehension by providing visual representations of abstract concepts (Mayer, 2018), making complex topics more accessible to diverse learners.

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that the lesson objectives are clear and well-defined; lesson plans promote the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of students and assess students' prior knowledge before beginning the lesson. Moreover, the presentation content is clear and easy to understand.
2. It is concluded that the presentation content is relevant to the learning objectives and I integrate opportunities for student collaboration and discussion in lesson plans. Moreover, the lesson plan activities promote active participation and understanding and activities engage students in the learning process.
3. It is concluded that the assessment effectively evaluates learning outcomes and the assigned homework is relevant to the material covered in class. Moreover, the homework assignments are clear and easy to understand and the prospective teacher demonstrates effective classroom management skills.
4. It is concluded that the prospective teacher well manages classroom behavior and the prospective teacher engages students well in the learning process. Moreover, the prospective teacher demonstrates the ability to handle the disruptive behavior of students and the prospective teacher maintains a positive learning environment.
5. It is concluded that the prospective teacher demonstrates a deep understanding of the subject matter and the prospective teacher provides clear explanations about the topic. Moreover, the prospective teacher uses appropriate AV aids to enhance understanding and the prospective teacher can answer students' questions accurately.

Recommendations

1. Prospective teachers may properly guide before they go to for teaching practice and their duties in the school may be mentioned to them and provided a chance to work on various school registers and given a chance in school administration.
2. The practicum school head, teaching staff, and other administrative staff may be guided appropriately about prospective teachers' strengths and areas of improvement to help them in teaching and other activities properly.

3. Prospective teachers may be provided with needed materials for teaching, proper practice over lesson plans, and AV aids may be provided to reduce the chances of errors, and also a pleasant, supportive, and friendly environment may be provided to prospective teachers to share and discuss with cooperative teachers.
4. Proper guidance instruction may be given to prospective teachers about pupil's behavior, discipline, feedback, and assessment problems.

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